

Enhancing Reliability: A Comprehensive Approach to Detecting and Monitoring
of Electrical Power Failures in Low Voltage Distribution Network.

by

ENOCK MOSE

DECLARATION.

I hereby declare that this work reflects all the activities and research done throughout this semester. The report gives a record of researched information on the chosen topic and it does not include any copied parts without the appropriate citation.

Sign -----.

Date: -----.

Declaration by Supervisor

Name:

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APPREVIATIONS/ ACRONYMS.

SCADA – Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition system.

IoT – Internet of Things.

PQ – Power Quality.

HRC – High Rupturing Capacity.

KPLC – Kenya Power & Lighting Company.

ABSTRACT.

Power failure on low voltage distribution lines became a significant challenge in many of the power utilities' lines. Research had shown that most power failures were due to the short-circuiting of power lines during heavy rains, lightning, the falling of tree branches on the lines, and overloading, which caused the HRC transformer fuses to blow. Generally, electric power systems are composed of generation, transmission, and distribution, which work in an interconnected manner to ensure the efficient distribution of electrical energy to customers. Of these, the generation and transmission parts were monitored using the SCADA system, unlike the low voltage distribution line from transformers to customers' consumer units. A challenge arose when power failed in remote areas where communication infrastructure is not efficient hence poor, which led to customers' inability to call utility companies' emergency teams to recover power on time.

The project proposed a low-cost power failure monitoring system on the LV distribution. The system employed a 250V ZMPT101B voltage sensor which was interfaced with a microcontroller, and the microcontroller was powered by a DC power supply. Voltage signals were sent to the ThingSpeak IoT web for remote monitoring of power at the substation. The sensor sent real-time distributed voltage from the distribution transformer to the IoT screen for analysis. IoT technology was deployed for this case, specifically ThingSpeak. On the ThingSpeak web screen, if the Red Indicator Power Monitor was ON, it signified power failure on the LV side, and if the Green Indicator Power Monitor was ON, it signified power distribution supply from the transformer was working normally. This system was beneficial to both consumers and utility companies to monitor any power failure on the customer LV side, thus reducing the time of recovery of energy to consumers through sending the emergency team on time.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background.

Fault is a deviation of a component operation from the expected manner. Therefore, fault can be physical, electrical, or environmental (Albert et al.,2019). Modern power systems are equipped with several protection schemes with the aim of avoiding the unpredicted events and power outages. By using all these schemes of protection, power systems still encounter emergency and mal-operation situations (Alhelou et al.,2019). Severe emergencies put the whole or a part of the system in danger. If the emergency is not well managed, the power system is likely to have severe cascading failures that might lead to a blackout in their operating areas (Alhelou et al.,2019).

Low-voltage distribution network power lines has a wider distribution range, their operating environment is complex, and it is easily affected by many factors which leads to line disconnection (Wei et al., 2023). In recent years there has been a significant, resurgent interest on LV power failure which led to blackouts in lower grid system. When faults occur in the traditional low-voltage distribution network, utility companies rely on manual inspection so as to find and solve faults that occurs on lower grid, but this method takes a lot of time and energy to recover power fault, this has led to researchers propose to use the Internet of things technology for optimization design on low voltage grid system (Wei et al., 2023).

Power transmission systems face unprecedented challenges due to the frequent extreme weather events which is the primary mechanism for the occurrence of cascading events, blackout events have unprecedented societal and economic impact. Stankovski et al., in their research report classifies the events based on following causes; Weather related: failure is directly caused by adverse weather conditions which include but not limited to windstorms, heavy snow, flooding, and extreme temperatures, sabotage of power cables, unintentional damage that occurs on road transport, and construction activities. Accident: which include trees falling on power lines due to old age or damage on poles by termite attack.

Moreover, voltage fluctuation or spikes or sag will cause the consumer's LV circuit breaker to trip; problems with power quality such as harmonics and reduced volts usually result in outages or failure of some consumers' electronics to work normally (Zhou, 2023).

These events had a pronounced economic impact and disrupted the lives of people (Stankovski et al., 2023). At the same time, the LV power distribution lines are directly connected with the user terminals, power supply and consumption of different users is also different. This will also have an impact on the normal operation of low-voltage lines. For example, in LV power supply and distribution lines, the occurrence of arc faults may be caused by aging of external insulation, poor contact and breakage of conductors. This will lead to power outage in the area (Wei et al 2019).

The widespread of electrical outages are symptoms of inadequate grid management practice and strategies. Analysis on power outages shows that it is not possible to avoid multiples of contingency initiated power outages, blackout propagation could and should be arrested, and restoration time could and should be reduced greatly through appropriate black start procedures (Imai et al., 2023). Until date, research has been centered on two areas of distribution network, the evolution of: high-voltage and medium-voltage transmission network automation and smart metering (Stanimirovic' et al., 2020).

The former research has been mainly focusing on improving service quality, studying and deploying fault location, isolation, and service restoration systems, whereas the latter is concerned with improving customer relationship management, increasing customer awareness, and enabling new smart home grid services. In most situations, low voltage (LV) network has been left out for long, considering the fact that this is the only network infrastructure that links the high voltages and medium-voltage to final consumers' residential buildings, and business premises (Stanimirovic et al., 2020).

The literature on LV monitoring is quite limited, and it is limited to a few results from experiments (Stanimirovic' et al.,2020). As such, Hoornaert et al. presented the practical verification of an LV distribution network voltage control system using a variety of devices with sensors in a single household. The developed control system utilized locally available materials found like the home supply voltage. The project depended on communication between various smart gadgets installed inside a room. Power system reliability is the capability of the electric grid system to reliably supply customers adequate electricity (Zhou., 2023).

The power distribution system is a fundamental aspect of the electric power system (Kousar, S.,2022). In order to deliver safe, efficient, reliable, and resilient power to

consumers, a distribution management system with the extension of the supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) system through a transmission network beyond the distribution network is used. These transmission networks oversee the distribution of energy generated at power plants to consumers via a complex system of transformers, substations, transmission lines, and distribution lines. The major challenges that exist on distribution management systems is, maintaining constant power loads, centralized communication, and malfunctioning of system equipments which lead to power outages.

Communication-less decentralised schemes for line protection are gaining popularity, they mostly depend upon the collected local measurements (Chhetija et. al.,2023). More importantly, the system must be able to connect with a number of separate measuring equipment, transmit the data between devices, store measured data, and produce the various analyses required for key decision making (Limpraptono et al.,2021). The wireless technology has evolved a lot during time, such that the technology can assure data transfer rates comparable with wired networks, and this type of communication is being protected, the security of this has been improved greatly. This way the wireless technology become the optimal solution for implementing, monitoring, and control systems in almost every sector and the electro energetic domain (Dobriceanu et al.,2020).

To address the problem of unknown power outages, the main objective outlined in this report was to design and develop a system capable of monitoring low voltage distribution networks. The main function was to monitor voltage to detect electrical power failures in the area, potentially caused by factors such as short-circuits, transformer overloading, or harmonics, leading to blackout scenarios on LV 240V distribution networks. Furthermore, the system aimed to alert the substation emergency team via MATLAB ThingSpeak Internet of Things (IoT) technology upon detecting any power outage.

Implementation of this system would enable utility companies to remotely monitor any power outages in real-time using IoT technology, thus eliminating the need for customers to report outages via phone calls.

1.2 Problem Statement.

Power failure can last for a long period of time, this may cause inconveniences to both customers and utilities companies by losing revenues. Power outage on the LV 240 V distribution network is not easily noticed at the substation level unlike that of the high transmission and generation power lines monitored through SCADA system. In case of outage, this leads to consumers remaining in blackout until the maintenance team are informed through phone calls from consumers to work on the faulty to recover power.

Most of the faulty that occur are communicated to utility company by customers who calls through specific numbers provided to report any failure and emergencies in their areas. In this case; if a customer fails to report the power failure due to poor communication network or any other case like one decide not to call, this will result to power companies' revenues reduction for energy is not consumed, consumers remaining in dark, and no work that depends on power will go on.

To enable utility companies to recover power in a very short period of time, the project is to be used in detecting and monitoring any power outage in real time, thus enabling the emergency team to be on toes recovering power to avoid any inconvenience. Research has been centered on two areas of distribution network: High-voltage transmission (132, and 400 kVs), and medium-voltage (33, and 66 kVs) transmission network which has led to its automation at substation, and smart metering and monitoring of the grid on the national control center.

1.3 Justification.

This project focused on designing and implementing an experimental NodeMCU microcontroller-based system capable of monitoring one of the electrical quantities: voltage. The voltage sensor (ZMPT101B) was embedded as the sensors to collect data from the field, continuously transmitting real-time data of LV power supply to the microcontroller. Subsequently, the data was processed and sent to an IoT cloud for remote monitoring of the voltage at the substation.

The project was conducted in three parts. Part one was completed prior to data collection and included the writing of an introduction that explained the working of the proposed

project, a literature review to synthesize research papers relevant to the topic, and a methodology outlining how the project was implemented.

Part two of the project focused on data collection and processing from the sensor, while part three comprised a final write-up of the project results and conclusions based on the collected data. The results and conclusions developed through the project would be used by organizations to improve their customer experience. Additionally, scholars and practitioners could utilize the results as foundational data regarding the monitoring of voltages from transformers for planned maintenance and research purposes.

1.4 Objectives.

1.4.1 Main objective.

The main objective of the project was to design and develop a system capable of monitoring voltage to detect electrical power outages on a 240V distribution network.

1.4.2 Specific Objectives.

1. Transition from the conventional method of power outage reporting, involving customer-initiated phone calls, to a real-time LV grid monitoring system at the substation.
2. Minimizing the restoration time for power outages, by ensuring prompt recovery for consumers by timely alerting the substation emergency team.
3. Mitigating revenue losses incurred by utility companies as a result of power outages and enhancing customer relationship management.
4. Monitor voltage fluctuations from distribution transformers.

1.5 Scope of Study.

The scope of the study was confined to the design and testing of a 240V low voltage network power lines monitor utilizing a voltage sensor interfaced with a microcontroller chip. The primary emphasis was on real-time monitoring of power to report any instances of power outage. Additionally, the research aimed to investigate the causes of power outages and explore available solutions to mitigate the problem.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW.

2.1 Reviewed Research Papers.

Khoa, N. M., et al., in their research paper had proposed an advanced Internet of Things (IoT) system for measuring, monitoring, and recording certain power quality (PQ) parameter for the micro-grid solutions. The proposed project system had both software and hardware included in the design and development where the hardware unit uses PZEM-004T modules with non-invasive current transformer (CT) sensors for sensing the PQ parameters, and an Arduino WeMos D1 R1 ESP8266 microcontroller which was used to receive data from the sensors and transmit it to the IoT server via the internet. By using Matlab software, an algorithm is created for the software unit to transmit measurement data to the ThingSpeak cloud. The suggested system has the capability to monitor and evaluate PQ parameters, such as active power, frequency, RMS current, root mean square (RMS) voltage, and the power factor of a low-voltage load in real-time. The results obtained from proposed system were usefully applied for monitoring and analysing PQ parameters (Khoa, et al., 2021).

In their 2021 research paper on Fault Location of Distributed Low voltage Distribution Network Based on Internet of Things, (Songnong Li, and Yan Zeng) had proposed fault location method in low-voltage network. The method is based on chaotic reflection method which will enable the real-time monitoring of power grid failure, contrast analysis of test results, which uses the principle of the shortest path with the shortest distance of fault point, set up by the recent test point measurements of potential fault branch collection, to determine the fault subnetwork, Then, multiple information sources in the fault subnetwork were fused to determine the specific fault branch, and the specific fault location was determined by the nearest test point. The project also implemented the fault detection and alarm system for low voltage distribution network which was designed on the basis of the power IoTs. Key technologies such as IED, LOLA wireless AD organization network and intelligent gateway are used in their project to realize the collection, communication, and real-time monitoring on mobile terminal through the cloud (Li., 2021).

R. M. Asif, S. R. Hassan, A. U. Rehman, A. U. Rehman, B. Masood and Z. A. Sher, (ICEET), Lahore, Pakistan 2020, did research on a fault occurrence in the underground cable line which led to development of a system which consisted of a microcontroller, LCD display,

fault sensing circuit module, Wi-Fi module, and power supply arrangement with regulated power output. Current in the circuit is sensed by the relays which are interconnected with the microcontroller. The fault sensing circuit is made with the combination of a set of series resistors and switches alongside each resistor. The proposed system was designed on the basis of simulated design. At the end, the fault was detected and its exact location had been shown on website (Asif et al., 2020).

Prof. Kiruthika K., et al. proposed a project which focused much on the efficiency of monitoring process of hybrid power system and fault detection. This project was implemented using microcontroller to make it automatic system. The main section of project included two sources, solar panel, wind section. Solar was to work in sunlight and wind will work in air flow. The wind motor output and main supply section output are connected with AC to DC converter for converting into pure DC. DC power from wind section was connected to CN6009 Booster then through relay to DC bus. The project is completely reliable on renewable energy sources on the generation part and monitor the power from solar and wind generation energy source through a DC microgrid implementation. The system uses sensors and controller for monitoring and detecting the possible faults that occur in the DC grid. Faults detected are indicated and in a swift the relay operates protecting the load from possible damage that could occur due to fault. The limitation of this project was that it did not provide remotely monitoring of the a.c power.

A short circuit in a network branch is assumed if the phase current reaches a magnitude above a threshold and stays above that threshold level for at least a certain duration in time. Detecting and locating single phase to earth faults is more problematic. Some prior art wireless sensor solutions have solved these issues by using specific hardware design, by constantly measuring and reporting phase current and voltage or through synchronizing sensors using the global positioning system (GPS). There are a number of disadvantages with these solutions such as continuous monitoring and reporting draw a great amount of energy. This solution has a number of drawbacks. A cable network cannot be retrofitted with the voltage sensors as it is prohibited to put any items on the sleeve of cable terminations or joints. The other two parallel phases and the ground capacitance will then greatly affect the reliability and sensitivity of the measurement, even if the phenomenon is computationally

compensated for. The same is recognized in overhead power line systems as well, especially when the phase angle should be determined.

2.2 Research Gap.

Unreported cases of power failure on low-voltage are a major challenge to both sectors that use power to drive the economy of a nation. There is no clear path of communication between the LV network power cables and the substation feeders in our network system, this has resulted to broken cables remaining on the ground for more than 6 hours thus posing a great danger to humans and animals in that area.

3 METHODOLOGY.

3.1 Research Method.

In this project report, an R&D methodology was employed to develop a 240 LV power outage and monitoring system. The method mainly consisted of two parts: The development of a system designed to measure voltage and acquire data from the LV power line. The creation of a ThingSpeak IoT channel monitor screen, intended to receive and display data graphically were crucial for the effective implementation of the power outage and monitoring system, facilitating real-time data collection, visualization, and analysis for enhanced monitoring and management of the LV power network.

3.2 Materials and Design.

The following are the material used to carry out this project:

3.2.1 Voltage sensor module.

ZMPT101B voltage sensor module was deployed, it is a voltage sensor made from the ZMPT101B voltage transformer.

3.2.1.1 Features of the Voltage Sensor.

The sensor has a ZMPT101B voltage transformer ideal to measure the single-phase AC voltage. It has high accuracy, good consistency for voltage and power measurement. It can measure up to 250V AC. It is simple to use and comes with a multi turn trim potentiometer for adjusting the analog-digital converter output.

Its features of measurement within 250V AC, onboard micro precision voltage transformer, good consistency for voltage and power measurement and high efficiency and accuracy, was a perfect match in implementing the project hence chosen.

Figure 3.1 ZMPT101B Voltage Sensor.

3.2.1.2 Sensor Calibration.

Sensor calibration is one of the most important aspects of energy monitoring. The measurement, control and management of electrical equipment are all dependent upon an accurate and reliable sensing. Moreover, the voltage and current are the fundamental quantities from which all other electrical quantities are determined.

The calibration of the sensor was accomplished by adjusting the voltage sensor's scale to accurately represent the voltage samples received from the ADC output. This calibration process entailed a comparison between the sensor's peak input voltage and its peak ADC output. The ESP8266 NodeMCU microcontroller was employed to process the ADC data and was specifically programmed to calculate the root mean square (RMS) value of the power supply's voltage.

Code Implementation.

```
/ Read the voltage and then print via Serial
float voltage = voltageSensor.getRmsVoltage();
Serial.println(voltage);
```

3.2.2 Microcontroller.

Figure 3.2 NodeMCU ESP8266 Development Board Microcontroller.

The ESP8266 is the name of a microcontroller designed by Espressif Systems. The ESP8266 itself is a self-contained WiFi networking solution offering as a bridge from existing microcontroller to WiFi and is also capable of running self-contained applications.

This module comes with a built in USB connector and a rich assortment of pin-outs. With a micro-USB cable, you can connect NodeMCU devkit to your laptop and flash it without any trouble.

3.2.2.1 Datasheet Specification of the Microcontroller

- ✓ Voltage:3.3V.
- ✓ Wi-Fi Direct (P2P), soft-AP.
- ✓ Current consumption: 10uA~170mA.
- ✓ Flash memory attachable: 16MB max (512K normal).
- ✓ Integrated TCP/IP protocol stack.
- ✓ Processor: Tensilica L106 32-bit.
- ✓ Processor speed: 80~160MHz.
- ✓ RAM: 32K + 80K.
- ✓ GPIOs: 17 (multiplexed with other functions).
- ✓ Analog to Digital: 1 input with 1024 step resolution.
- ✓ +19.5dBm output power in 802.11b mode
- ✓ 802.11 support: b/g/n.
- ✓ Maximum concurrent TCP connections: 5.

3.2.3 Power supply.

A 5V DC power supply was used to power the module and sensor

3.2.4 ThingSpeak Internet of Things web account.

Figure 3.3 ThingSpeak Channel.

3.3 System Design Concept.

Figure 3.1 Conceptual Block Diagram of the System

The sensor was installed directly after the distribution transformer LV network outgoing power lines to gather data effectively. However, installing the sensors necessitated a significant cabling effort, prompting consideration for IoT wireless sensors as a promising alternative. Embracing IoT technology holds the promise of efficient fault management and monitoring of electrical distribution networks, aligning with the objectives of today's smart cities.

3.4 Hardware Design

This part of the report presents the hardware design for monitoring voltage levels and transmitting data to ThingSpeak using an ESP8266 module. The design incorporated the required components and connections were made to achieve the desired functionality.

3.4.1 The Hardware Setup:

3.4.1.1 ESP8266 NodeMCU Development Board

Acted as the main microcontroller and handled Wi-Fi connectivity for wireless communication to the IOT.

It was connected as follows:

- ESP8266 module was connected to a power supply.
- We established connections for programming and WiFi router connections.
- The USB-to-Serial adapter was connected for programming and debugging.

3.4.1.2 Voltage Sensor (ZMPT101B)

It was used to measure voltage levels from the power line, provided analog output signals proportional to the measured voltage. It was connected as follows: The output pin of the voltage sensor was connected to an analog input pin of the ESP8266 module, the ground pin of the voltage sensor was connected to the ground pin of the ESP8266 module.

3.4.1.3 Power Supply

5V DC power supply or batteries provided power to the ESP8266 module and voltage sensor. This was done in consideration to the compatibility with the voltage and current datasheets requirements of the components deployed.

3.4.1.4 Connections

The connections were established as follows and were facilitated by the jumper wires: Connected the analog output pin OUT of the voltage sensor to pin A0 of the ESP8266 module. Connected the ground pin GND of the voltage sensor to the ground pin GND of the ESP8266 module. Connected the power supply to the ESP8266 module to provide power to the module.

3.4.2 Testing and Validation

Thorough testing of the hardware setup was conducted to: Perform calibration of the sensor to ensure accurate readings from the voltage sensor in real world voltage values.

3.5 Software Design.

3.5.1 System Overview

The required components, including ESP8266 NodeMCU Development Board, Voltage Sensor (ZMPT101B), power supply, jumper wires, and USB-to-Serial adapter (for programming and debugging), were gathered. The system aims to monitor voltage levels using an ESP8266 module connected to a voltage sensor and transmit the data to ThingSpeak IoT platform for real-time visualization and analysis.

ESP8266 Module: Handles Wi-Fi connectivity and communication with ThingSpeak.
Voltage Sensor: Measures voltage level from the power line. ThingSpeak IoT Platform: Received and stored LV voltage data, provided a web interface for visualization and analysis of data.

3.5.2 Software Architecture:

3.5.2.1 ESP8266 Firmware

It is responsible for reading voltage signal data from the sensor and sending them it to ThingSpeak. The project utilized the Arduino IDE for development and programming of the ESP8266 module.

3.5.2.2 Communication Protocol

The software utilizes communication protocols such as Wi-Fi (e.g., TCP/IP) for establishing connectivity with ThingSpeak servers over the internet. Utilizes HTTP protocol to send data to ThingSpeak' s REST API which stands for REpresentational State Transfer. It's an architectural style for developing web services. A lot of people believe that REST is one of many IoT protocols. However, REST itself is a development concept, not an IoT protocol.

3.5.3 Integration with ThingSpeak:

3.5.3.1 ThingSpeak Channel Setup

ThingSpeak account and channel was created with appropriate fields for storing sampled sensor voltage data. After creating the channel, API keys was generated for authentication and data transmission.

3.5.3.2 Data Transmission

Voltage data from the sensor read and formatted for transmission to ThingSpeak. ThingSpeak API keys and code below was used to send data to the channel at regular intervals 15 seconds.

Send data to ThingSpeak

```
if (WiFi.status() == WL_CONNECTED) {  
    //ThingSpeak.writeField(channelID, 1, realWorldVoltage, apiKey.c_str ());  
  
    ThingSpeak.writeField(channelID, 1, voltageStr.toFloat(), apiKeyPtr);  
} else {  
    Serial.println("WiFi not connected. Cannot send data to ThingSpeak");  
}
```

3.5.3.3 Visualization and Monitoring of Voltage Data

This allowed the users to visualize and make analysis based on real-time voltage data received using the ThingSpeak web screen interface. MATLAB provided customizable charts, widgets, and graphs for monitoring LV trends over a period of time.

3.5.4 Security Measures

3.5.4.1 Wi-Fi Security

Ensured safe data transmission thus secured Wi-Fi communication by using encrypted connections (e.g., WPA2).

3.5.4.2 ThingSpeak Security

This protected data transmission to ThingSpeak using HTTPS protocol. Utilized API keys for authentication and access control of data.

3.5.5 Programming

C/C++: is the programming language used for programming the ESP8266 module. C/C++ allows for low-level hardware interaction and efficient memory management, making it well-suited for embedded systems development.

Arduino Language

Arduino language (based on C/C++) is commonly used for programming the ESP8266 module, especially when using the arduino IDE. It provided a simplified syntax and extensive libraries for interfacing with hardware.

ESP8266 Core for Arduino

This framework extends the arduino framework to support the ESP8266 module, providing additional libraries and tools for programming and interacting with the ESP8266 hardware.

ESP8266WiFi Library

This library is used for configuring the ESP8266 module to connect to Wi-Fi networks. It provides functions for managing Wi-Fi connections, configuring network parameters, and handling network-related events.

ThingSpeak Library

ThingSpeak Library facilitates communication with the ThingSpeak IoT platform. It includes functions for sending data to ThingSpeak channels, managing API keys, and handling communication errors. Arduino code was written to read voltage data from the analog pin A0 of the sensor and transmit it to ThingSpeak using the ESP8266 module. The Wi-Fi connectivity setup was implemented using the ESP8266WiFi library, and data transmission to ThingSpeak was facilitated using the ThingSpeak library.

3.5.6 Testing and Validation:

3.5.6.1 Testing

Testing was conducted to verify the functionality of each component (e.g., sensor reading, Wi-Fi connectivity) and sensor calibration to get desired voltages.

3.5.6.2 Data Processing

The software includes algorithms to process raw voltage data obtained from the sensor. This processing involves scaling the raw sensor readings to obtain accurate voltage measurements within the desired range (e.g., 220V to 250V).

4 RESULTS.

The fault detection process is initiated when the sensor registers a voltage signal nearing less 200V, indicating a fault condition. This occurrence typically coincides with the disruption of the distribution transformer's protective HRC fuse, resulting in an open circuit in the network line. Upon detecting the loss of voltage load, the sensor infers the presence of a fault. Specifically, it presumes a short circuit between phases, pinpointing the line segment connecting the red phase to either the yellow or blue phase. Verification of the fault is achieved by comparing voltage measurements obtained during the fault event.

Figure 4.1 Power ON Indicator Results

On the ThingSpeak screen web, if the Red Indicator Power Monitor was ON, it signified a power outage on the LV side. Conversely, if the Green Indicator Power Monitor was turned ON, it indicated that power distribution supply from the transformer was functioning normally. This system proved beneficial to both consumers and utility companies like KPLC in Kenya for monitoring any power failures on the customer LV side, thereby reducing the recovery time of energy to consumers by promptly dispatching emergency teams.

On thingspeak screen web, if the Red Indicator Power Monitor is ON: signify the power outage on the LV side or voltages are at low levels not within the desired range and if the Green Indicator Power Monitor is turned ON: signify power distribution supply from the transformer is working normally. This system will be beneficial to both consumers and utility company like KPLC in Kenya to monitor any power failure on customer LV side thus reducing the time of recovery of energy to consumers through sending the emergency team on time.

Figure 4.2 Power Failure Indicator is ON.

5 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RESEARCH.

5.1 Conclusion

In this study, the main objective was to design and develop a system to monitor voltage for detecting electrical power outages. Key findings from the project study revealed that the LV network was the primary infrastructure connecting to customers on a larger scale, and power failures on the LV side were a global issue that needed to be addressed. Consumers typically reported any outages since they were not extensively monitored.

An innovative setup was proposed to replace the traditional method of power outage reporting, where consumers called by phone to report outages, with real-time LV grid monitoring at the substation level. This approach aimed to reduce the restoration time of power outages to consumers as quickly as possible by alerting the substation emergency team.

The project operated with reference to single-phase voltage measurement. Data on ThingSpeak could be downloaded and stored for research purposes.

The proposed software design provides a framework for monitoring voltage levels using an ESP8266 module, transmitting the data to ThingSpeak web account for visualization and analysis. It ensures security, reliability, and ease of use, making it suitable for deployment in various applications, including smart grid monitoring and Internet of Things projects.

5.2 Future Research

In order to improve the study of power failures in low voltage distribution networks, this paper proposes future research approaches that make use of a three-phase voltage and current sensors which are available in the market. To improve fault detection, localization, and restoration procedures in distribution networks, the most effective sensor technologies are those being recognized for their efficient performance. This report outlines research such as the creation of fault-tolerant systems, real-time monitoring approaches, machine learning algorithms for failure prediction and classification, and sensor data fusion techniques. For effective tackling this very complex difficulties linked to power failures requires collaboration amongst academia, industrial stakeholders, and utility company providers.

1. Machine Learning Algorithms for Fault Prediction and Classification

The application of machine learning techniques in the field of technology presents great potential for improving fault classification and prediction in low voltage distribution networks. These algorithms can be trained to identify patterns suggestive of approaching power outages by utilizing past sensor data, allowing for preventative actions to minimize disruptions.

Choosing the right sensors to provide the necessary data inputs for the machine learning models is a crucial step in this process, ADE7753 stands out as the best option. The ADE7753 sensor is well-known for its accurate voltage and current readings thus possess strong energy metering capabilities, providing the ideal balance of precision, efficiency, dependability, and adaptability. It has a capacity to blend with the existing distribution networks infrastructure, together with extensive It is therefore, suited to power machine learning algorithms that aim to forecast and classify faults because of its data collecting functionalities.

2. Sensor Data Fusion Techniques

Combining data from several sensors is a significant step forward for fault location and detection in low voltage distribution networks. Through the integration of data obtained from many sources, including three-phase voltage and current sensors, engineers can achieve a thorough comprehension of network dynamics and anticipate possible places of failure. Allegro Microsystems' ACS758 is a model option for data fusion applications that require the best performance possible. The ACS758 sensor, well-known for its accuracy and dependability in current sensing applications, provides unmatched phase-by-phase accuracy for recording electrical characteristics.

6 BUDGET.

<i>Item</i>	<i>Purpose of item</i>	<i>Cost per unit</i>	<i>Shipping cost</i>	<i>No. of units</i>	<i>Total cost (Kshs)</i>
Microcontroller (NodeMCU ESP8266 WiFi Development Board)	Read the data from the voltage and send the results to the IoT cloud	1,000	180	1	1,180
250 ZMPT101B Voltage sensor	Voltage measurement	500	300	1	800
Total (Shs)		1,500	480	2	1,980

Table 6.1 Budget.

7 WORKING SCHEDULE.

SEMESTER 1														
ACTIVITY	WEEKS													
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
Project proposal orientation														
Concept Idea generation based on solving industrial problem.														
Project conception (Topic, Title)														
Literature review														
Preliminary proposal (methodology, expected results, budget)														
Preliminary proposal presentation.														

Table 7.2 Working Schedule for semester one.

SEMESTER 2															
ACTIVITY	WEEKS														
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	
Product specifications and requirements															
Bi-monthly meetings with supervisor															
Building and testing of prototypes															
Report writing															
Presentation of the project.															
Report submission															

Table 7.3 Working Schedule for semester two.

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